

PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 12 LEARNERS IN 21ST CENTURY LITERATURE FROM THE PHILIPPINES AND THE WORLD: BASIS FOR ENHANCEMENT ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. This study aimed to develop and propose enhancement activities to improve the performance of Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World at PIMSAT Colleges San Carlos City Campus during the first semester of, the school year 2020–2021. The proposed enhancement activities in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World were evaluated by the pool of expert Senior High School English 12 teachers and the Senior High School Coordinators of the different private schools in San Carlos City Division that offer Senior High School Programs. The mean percentage score was used to determine the level of performance of the Grade 12 learners during the first semester of, the school year 2020–2021. Their average mean percentage score for the two quarters is 47.35% which is below the DepEd standard of 75%. The overall average weighted mean was used to describe the evaluation of the two groups of evaluators of the proposed enhancement activities. The proposed enhancement activities in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World were “highly acceptable” with an overall average weighted mean of 3.83 based on the evaluation of the following factors: content, format presentation, and organization. Teachers should evaluate learners’ level of performance to identify their least mastered competencies. Teachers should develop enhancement activities to improve learners’ level of performance. It is recommended that the proposed enhancement activities should be used by Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World for better learning outcomes.

Keywords. Enhancement Activities, Performance Level, Least Mastered Competencies, Acceptability Level

1 Introduction

Literature provides the mirror of what life is all about and gives a lasting realization in understanding the world. It also serves as an avenue to language teaching and developing both the reading and writing skills among learners. The famous American author, Henry Van Dyke, described literature as the collection of writing which interpret the meanings of nature and life in artistic forms of permanent interest. Literature also provides the ability of humankind to appreciate the things around him/her to have a more positive outlook on what life is and what it will be in the future. It makes a person see beauty, love, and harmony.

Wijaya (2012) considered literary texts such as poems, songs, and short stories which are used in language teaching. Literary texts provide authentic texts with different language styles and registers which allow learners to have a wide range of learning and understanding language. Additionally, Stan (2015) asserts students use literary texts not only for information but also to interpret them and decode their meanings. Hence, literature becomes an effective medium of teaching language. Literature provides authentic language learning experiences by using literary texts where learners can learn new words, syntax, discourse, sentence patterns, and other writing skills.

Literature teaching and genre-based pedagogies offer a valuable resource for assisting students’ ability to both comprehend and produce their texts because of the opportunity for them to integrate personal ideas, thoughts, and experiences that can be connected with what they are reading (Almacioglu and Okan, 2018). Literature plays an important role in developing language learning. Literature is a way of developing multiple literacies and thinking skills which are vital for learners to acquire 21st-century skills like critical thinking (Naji, 2019 et al.).

In the Philippines, literacy is important for the Filipinos. One way of making this possible is by giving much importance to education to its people. Literature, as part of the subjects being taken in the schools, serves as a medium for language

teaching and learning. It promotes the development of literacy as well as the preservation and transmission of values, customs, and traditions that reflect our very own culture.

Rosales (2016) pointed out in his book, *English for Specific Purposes*, that reading is a part of teaching and learning literature that gives fresh delights and insights that can open a new world of meaningful experiences for the students. Literature appeal should be lasting and universal. Thus, there is the recognition of putting whatever perspective to discover personal and cultural experiences to understand better the people of other cultures in the attainment of harmony and world peace.

He further elaborated that literature has been an authentic instrument used by teachers in teaching language lessons. It is said that language and literature learning is more than strictly an intellectual process of reading a selection or just memorizing vocabulary and analyzing grammar. It calls for critical reading and thinking skills, as well as analyzing, evaluating, or giving judgment to the text read. Successful language and literature learning should enlist emotion so that students will be moved to read and engage themselves in critical reading, writing, and thinking. When learners make their essays based on a literary piece that they have read, they are applying problem-solving skills in which they become critical thinkers. Perez-Grajo (2019) claimed that studying the literature of the nation plays an important role for its inhabitants understand themselves by knowing their cultural background and heritage. Literature preserves every nation and enables diversity among its people.

When learners find pleasure in studying literature and reading different literary texts, they will have higher vocabulary, better reading comprehension, and improved communication skills most especially in their speaking and writing abilities which will enable them to express themselves. Therefore, because of the significant functions and contributions of literature in the lives of the people, learners' education, and effective language teaching and learning, the importance of literature cannot be denied. That is why literature is also included as a compulsory subject that aims to instill values and to develop a strong foundation of knowledge of a certain language like the English language.

Moses (2019) et al posited that English is an international and in-demand language today. Most of the literary texts published are written in English language. As learners engage themselves in learning activities they have to do after reading literary text such as answering comprehension questions, reflection papers, and the like, they begin to encounter problems and difficulties in expressing themselves in English. They cannot organize their ideas into meaningful compositions because of a lack of words to use inability to recognize meanings and limited knowledge of what literary forms are and what are these all about.

These difficulties were also observed among Grade 12 learners who took up 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World in PIMSAT Colleges San Carlos City Campus where the researcher was assigned to teach the subject. This learning area serves as a literature subject in the Senior High School which involves learners in varied reading and writing activities. It enables the learners to develop their ability to read and comprehend texts and other reading materials and to write creatively to express themselves effectively. Hence, necessary interventions have to be done to make learners love reading literature while promoting language learning.

The modules being used by PIMSAT Colleges San Carlos City Campus are the modules coming from the main campus located in Dagupan City. The researcher believed that the activities found in their modules can still be enhanced for the PIMSAT Colleges San Carlos City Campus Grade 12 learners in pursuit of better learning outcomes. Because of this, the researcher became motivated to develop and propose additional learning material for the Grade 12 learners which can be used to address the least mastered competencies they encounter in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World. Even in this time of pandemic, there is a strong need for quality education to be delivered to the learners. Teachers can come up with enhancement activities that aim to help students to learn effectively and master a skill or competency. In the absence of face-to-face classes, remediation can be done by providing additional activities that will enhance the amount of learning that learners have achieved in answering their modules. Aside from modules, enhancement activities could serve as a reference to learners in reviewing their lessons which will enable teachers to have better learning outcomes from the learners.

It is therefore along this context of discussion that the researcher was propelled to conduct this study. The development of enhancement activities that can be used to improve student's learning in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World is imperative.

2 Review of Related Literature

The foreign studies of Mart (2018), David (2018) et al, Bland (2018), Calafato (2018), and Sudirman (2018) reviewed in this chapter, provided the researcher with additional insights that have contributed a lot to the conduct of this study. Their studies gave the researcher further realizations in the importance of studying literature as a means of values integration and building a strong foundation of language learning specifically the English language.

The present study has similarities and differences with the related studies presented in this chapter. These related studies differ in terms of subjects and locale, learning materials and resources proposed, and research designs employed. The studies of Aquino (2019), Bernal (2019), and Narag (2019) are similar to the present study in terms of the proposed learning materials that could be used to address learners' difficulties and improve English instruction. They focused on the use of electronic and computer-assisted learning resources in teaching and learning English and improving reading comprehension as well. This study differs from them because the researcher proposed printed learning materials to address the least mastered competencies of Grade 12 learners in 21st-century Century Literature from the Philippines and the World.

In like manner, the studies of Diaz (2019) and Resngit (2018) are similar to the present study in terms of the proposed learning materials. They gave much importance to improving learners' comprehension level and spelling skills utilizing intervention materials whereas the present researcher proposed printed enhancement activities for 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World.

The study of Palisoc (2018) made use of printed learning to improve the performance level of Grade 9 learners in Araling Panlipunan which is similar to the present study. They differ in subject area focus, grade level, and the learning competencies targeted. The present study is different from the above-mentioned studies because enhancement activities proposed by the researcher were based on the least mastered competencies of Grade 12 learners in 21st-century Century Literature from the Philippines and the World. This study is also considered a novel endeavor because its output (Enhancement Activities) will be used by the learners in the new normal setup of education brought about by the pandemic.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive-developmental method of research. It is descriptive because the researcher employed an in-depth analysis of the first and second quarterly examination results in 21st-century Century Literature from the Philippines and the World to describe the level of performance and to identify the least mastered competencies of Grade 12 learners. The descriptive method was utilized in this research because it dealt with counting, measuring, and describing data.

This study also employed the developmental method of research because the researcher proposed and developed enhancement activities for use of the Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World. Enhancement activities proposed and developed focused on activities that will address the identified least mastered competencies of the Grade 12 learners. This study also utilized this method because the researcher went through a systematic design, developing, and evaluating the proposed enhancement activities through a specific set of criteria.

3.2 Sources of Data

The first and second quarterly examination results were used by the researcher in determining the level of performance and in identifying the least mastered competencies of the Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World during the first semester of, the school year 2020-2021. The analysis of the first and second quarterly

examination results served as the basis for the preparation and development of the enhancement activities for the use of learners in the said subject.

The evaluation of the proposed enhancement activities was made by the private Senior High School English 12 teachers and the Senior High School Coordinators from the selected nine (9) private secondary schools in San Carlos City offering Senior High School Programs that are near the City proper to ensure researcher's safety in this unprecedented time.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To determine the level of performance of the Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World, the first and second quarterly examination results were used by the researcher. The mean percentage score (MPS) was used to describe the learners' level of performance.

The DepEd-prescribed computation for the mean percentage score was employed by the researcher and described based on the computed MPS of the first and second quarterly examination results.

The least mastered competencies of the Grade 12 learners in 21st-century Century Literature from the Philippines and the World were determined by conducting an item analysis of the first and second quarterly examination results. The percentage of correct response (PCR) was used to identify the least mastered competencies of Grade 12 learners. The results of the itemized analysis were described using the DepEd-prescribed computation for a level of mastery.

To determine the level of acceptability of the proposed enhancement activities, the average weighted mean (AWM) was used. Results were interpreted using a 4-point scale.

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Level of Performance of Grade 12 Learners in 21st-Century Literature from the Philippines and the World

Table 1 presents the summarized data in terms of the mean percentage scores (MPS) for each quarter. It can be gleaned from the table that during the first quarterly examination, there was a mean percentage score of 53.48%. The mean percentage score obtained by the Grade 12 learners is below the prescribed mastery level of 75% by the Department of Education.

Table 1 also reflects that the mean percentage score of the Grade 12 learners decreased to 41.22% in the second quarterly examination. The average MPS for the first and second quarterly examinations is 47.35. It could be deduced that the level of performance attained by the Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World did not meet the required mastery level of 75% as prescribed by the Department of Education.

Results show that for the past two quarterly examinations during the first semester school year 2020-2021 the mean percentage scores obtained by the Grade 12 learners were all below the prescribed mastery level. It can be noted that the results are alarming as far as quality education is concerned. Grade 12 learners may have poor academic standing when results like this continue which will also affect their college admission. This calls for interventions to be used by the teachers to enhance the performance of Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World.

Table 1. First and Second Quarterly Examination Results
 During the First Semester (2020-2021)

N=23

PIMSAT COLLEGES INC. (SHS) Grade 12	FIRST QUARTERLY EXAMINATION	SECOND QUARTERLY EXAMINATION	AVERAGE MPS	DESCRIPTIVE EQUIVALENT
	MPS	MPS		
	53.48%	41.22%	47.35%	AVERAGE MASTERY

4.2 Least Mastered Competencies of Grade 12 Learners in 21st-Century Literature from the Philippines and the World

The researcher conducted an item analysis of the first and second quarterly examination results for the first semester school year 2020-2021. Table 2 reveals the least mastered competencies of Grade 12 learners in 21st-century Century Literature from the Philippines and the World based on the learning competencies given in the first and second quarterly examinations.

Table 2. Identified Least Mastered Competencies of Grade 12 Learners in 21st-Century Literature from the Philippines and the World Based on the First and Second Quarterly Examination Results First Semester (2020-2021)

Lessons/ Competencies First Quarter Examination	Percentage of Correct Response (PCR)	Description
1. Understanding Literature and literary genres during the Pre-colonial to the Contemporary Period <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the geographic, linguistic, and ethnic dimensions of Philippine literary history from pre-colonial to the contemporary (EN12Lit-Ia-21) 	55.652	Not Mastered
2. Recognizing Major Literary Texts and Genres <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compare and contrast various 21st century literary genres and the ones from the earlier genres/periods citing their elements, structures and traditions (EN12Lit-Id-25) 	55.217	Not Mastered
3. Understanding Meanings: Figures of Speech and Idiomatic Expressions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the figures of speech and other literary techniques and devices in the text (EN12Lit-le-27) 	34.782	Not Mastered
Lessons/ Competencies Second Quarter Examination	Percentage of Correct Response (PCR)	Description
4. Identifying Philippine Literature from the Regions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do a self and/or peer-assessment of the creative adaptation of a literary text, based on rationalized criteria, prior to presentation (EN12Lit-le-31.3) 	43.144	Not Mastered
5. Identifying 21 st Century Literary Genres <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compare and contrast various 21st century literary genres and their elements, structures, and traditions from across the globe (EN12Lit-IId-25) 	42.391	Not Mastered
6. Analyzing meanings of texts by applying critical reading strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify representative texts and authors from each region (e.g. engage in oral history research with focus on key personalities from the students' region/province/town) (EN12-Ila-22) 	30.435	Not Mastered
7. Evaluating 21st Century Literatures of the World through their representative texts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do a self and peer-assessment of the creative adaptation of a literary text, based on rationalized criteria, prior to presentation (EN12Lit-IIij-31.3) 	38.261	Not Mastered
8. Valuing Philippine National Artists, their Works and Contributions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value the contributions of local writers to the development of the regional literary traditions (EN12Lit-Ic-23) 	53.478	Not Mastered

As shown in Table 2, the obtained percentage of correct response (PCR) for each of the given learning competencies in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World is below the 75% standard set by DepEd. It could be noted that the Grade 12 learners manifested “no mastery” in all the learning competencies based on the computed percentage of correct responses.

It could be inferred that because of the limited learning materials that learners can use, they tend to have a very limited understanding and mastery of their lessons which leads to poor performance in the quarterly tests. Given these findings,

there is a felt need for teachers to employ other learning materials that could help the learners understand and master their lessons very well.

Based on the results reflected in the same table, the 8 least mastered competencies by the Grade 12 learners became the basis for the development of enhancement activities in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World.

4.3 Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Enhancement Activities in 21st-Century Literature from the Philippines and the World

The basis in the preparation and development of enhancement activities in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World were the 8 identified least mastered competencies of Grade 12 learners in the first and second quarterly examination results during the first semester, school year 2020-2021. The proposed enhancement activities were evaluated by the seventeen (17) private Senior High School English 12 teachers and the eight (8) Senior High School Coordinators from the selected nine (9) private schools in San Carlos City, Pangasinan offering Senior High School Program. The evaluation was based on the DepEd-prescribed evaluation instrument for printed materials with the following factors: content, format presentation, and organization.

4.4 Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Enhancement Activities as Evaluated by the Private Senior High School English 12 Teachers

The first group of evaluators of the proposed enhancement activities was the private Senior High School English 12 teachers. Table 4A reflects the results of the evaluation made by the English 12 teachers on the level of acceptability of the proposed enhancement activities based on the given factors namely: content, format presentation, and organization.

It could be gleaned from the same table that Factor 1 obtained an average weighted mean of 3.77, Factor 2, 3.79, and Factor 3, 3.75 respectively. All the indicators under the three factors were rated "highly acceptable". Based on the evaluation made by the SHS English 12 teachers, the proposed enhancement activities were all rated "highly acceptable" with an overall average weighted mean of 3.77.

It could be deduced that the teacher-respondents found the proposed enhancement activities in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World appropriate for use by Grade 12 learners and could improve their level of performance.

4.5 Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Enhancement Activities as Evaluated by the Senior High School Coordinators

The SHS Coordinators rated the proposed enhancement activities with an almost perfect mean of 4. Factor 1 obtained an average weighted mean of 3.84, factor 2 being the highest among the three factors with an average weighted mean of 3.91 and factor 3 with an average weighted mean of 3.88. All the given factors and their respective indicators were rated and described as "highly acceptable".

As a whole, the results of the evaluation of the proposed enhancement activities in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World by the Senior High School Coordinators are described as "highly acceptable" as shown by the computed overall average weighted mean of 3.88.

4.6 Summary of Evaluation of the Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Enhancement Activities by the Senior High School English 12 Teachers and the Senior High School Coordinators

As reflected in Table 3, the evaluation made by the SHS English 12 teachers of the proposed enhancement activities obtained an overall average weighted mean of 3.77 and is described as "highly acceptable". In like manner, the SHS Coordinators rated the proposed enhancement activities as "highly acceptable" with an overall average weighted mean of 3.88. The proposed enhancement activities garnered a combined overall average weighted mean of 3.83 described as "highly acceptable".

Table 3. Summary of Evaluation of the Proposed Enhancement Activities
As Evaluated by the Senior High School English Teachers
and the Senior High School Coordinators
N=25

Evaluators	Factors	AVWM	OAWM	DE
SHS English 12 Teachers	Content	3.77	3.77	HA
	Format	3.79		
	Presentation and Organization	3.75		
SHS Coordinators	Content	3.84	3.88	HA
	Format	3.91		
	Presentation and Organization	3.88		
Combined OAWM			3.83	HA

It could be deduced from the same table that both the two groups of evaluators rated the proposed enhancement activities as “highly acceptable” for use of Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World. Hence, Senior High School English teachers must be encouraged to develop learning materials that could help improve the performance of the learners. School administrators should also plan and conduct training and workshops that could improve teachers’ ability to design and create other learning materials to address learners’ difficulties in understanding their lessons.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The mean percentage scores for the first and second quarterly examinations are 53.48% and 41.22% respectively. The average mean percentage score for the two quarters is 47.35% which is below the DepEd standard of 75%. The least mastered competencies of Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World and their computed percentage of correct responses are 1) understanding Literature and literary genres during the Pre-colonial to the Contemporary Period (55.652), 2) recognizing Major Literary Texts and Genres (55.217), 3) understanding meanings: Figures of Speech and Idiomatic Expressions (34.782), 4) identifying Philippine Literature from the Regions (43.144), 5) identifying 21st Century Literary Genres (42.391), 6) analyzing meanings of texts by applying critical reading strategies (3.435), 7) evaluating 21st Century Literature of the World through their representative texts (38.261), and 8) valuing Philippine National Artists, their Works, and Contributions (53.478).

The proposed Enhancement Activities in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World were developed and proposed based on the identified least mastered competencies of the Grade 12 learners. The level of acceptability of the proposed enhancement activities in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World for use of Grade 12 learners is 3.83 which is “highly acceptable” based on the evaluation results of the private Senior High School English Teachers (3.77) and the Senior High School Coordinators (3.88).

There is a need to improve the performance of Grade 12 learners in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World. Grade 12 learners have the least mastered competencies in 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World. The proposed enhancement activities in 21st-Century Literature from the Philippines and the World are suitable for the use of Grade 12 learners and could improve their level of performance.

Teachers should evaluate learners’ level of performance to identify their least mastered competencies. Teachers should develop enhancement activities to improve learners’ level of performance. The proposed enhancement activities should be recommended for the use of Grade 12 learners as instructional material to have better learning outcomes. Similar studies should be conducted in other learning areas and other grade levels to improve learners’ performance.

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